

Damage detection using Direct-Write Piezoelectric Transducers and Lamb Waves in Composite Materials

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1) Introduction

Carbon-Fibre Reinforced Polymer:
progressive failure and hidden damage
→ **Structural Health Monitoring:**
✓ Improve safety
✓ Reduce cost of repair
✓ Reduce inspection time

Direct-Write Transducers:
✓ Batch fabrication, consistency
✓ Low profile and weight
✓ No bonding agent
✓ Scalable

Previous applications of **DWT** on **CFRP** used BaTiO₃ [2] or PZT [3] particles in polymer matrix for passive sensing of impact

	PZT	PVDF
Heavy metal		Polymer
> 1000°C		135°C
7.5-8.0 g/cm ³		1.78 g/cm ³
Brittle		Flexible

2) Fabrication

➤ Effective d_{33} of -12 pm/V (LSV at 1.5 kHz)

$$d_{33} = \frac{\text{displacement}}{\text{voltage}}$$

Objectives:

- Apply DWT on CFRP plate by in-situ deposition, crystallization and patterning of P(VDF-TrFE) coatings
- Develop mode selection through top electrode pattern design
- Use DWT on CFRP for active sensing

3) Top electrode pattern: Mode selection

Excitation: 5 tone burst sinusoidal + Hanning window, at 100 Vpp
Resonant frequency of the plate: 74 kHz

❖ Discrete PZT transducers glued on surface:

Wavelength λ (mm)	Theoretical frequency A ₀ mode (kHz)
2	676
4	325
6	208
8	148
10	112
12	88

❖ DWT with electrode periodicities of 8, 10 and 12 mm:

- A₀ mode selected at theoretical values
- Amplitudes decrease for higher frequencies (smaller λ)

4) Damage detection

Wave interaction with damage

▪ LSV scans – bottom of the plate, signal sent with 40 Vpp at 74 kHz (A₀ mode)

Signal differences for path 2-4

5) Conclusion and further work

- ✓ Polymer **DWT** designed and fabricated on **CFRP** plates with good piezoelectric response, but low amplitude
- ✓ Ability to select modes through top electrode pattern
- ✓ Ability to detect 25 mm impact damage with electrode periodicity of 12 mm
- ❑ Finite elements modeling for understanding of wave propagation
- ❑ Damage localisation method
- ❑ Advantages of using **DWT** compared to discrete transducers

References

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Acknowledgments

- A*STAR Research Attachment Programme (ARAP)
- IMRE authors acknowledges partial support by SMI AIM R&D Programme, Project ID: SMI-2015-OF-01, and Maritime Sustainability R&D Programme, Project ID: SMI-2015-MA-07